

Real-Time Guarantees for Critical Traffic in IEEE 802.1Qbv TSN Networks with Unscheduled and Unsynchronized End-Systems

Mohammadreza Barzegaran ✉

Technical University of Denmark Kongens Lyngby, Denmark

Niklas Reusch ✉

Technical University of Denmark Kongens Lyngby, Denmark

Luxi Zhao ✉

Technical University of Munich, Munich, Germany

Silviu S. Craciunas ✉

TTTech Computertechnik AG, Vienna, Austria

Paul Pop ✉

Technical University of Denmark Kongens Lyngby, Denmark

Abstract

Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) aims to extend the IEEE 802.1Q Ethernet standard with real-time and time-aware capabilities. Each device’s transmission of time-critical frames is done according to a so-called Gate Control List (GCL) schedule via the timed-gate mechanism described in IEEE 802.1Qbv. Most schedule generation mechanisms for TSN have a constraining assumption that both switches and end-systems in the network must have at least the TSN capabilities related to scheduled gates and time synchronization. However, many TSN networks use off-the-shelf end-systems, e.g., for providing sensor data, which are not scheduled and/or synchronized.

In this paper, we propose a more flexible scheduling strategy that considers a worst-case delay analysis within the scheduling synthesis step, leveraging the solution’s optimality to support TSN networks with unscheduled and unsynchronized end-systems while still being able to guarantee bounded latency for critical messages. Our method enables real-world systems that feature off-the-shelf microcontrollers and sensor nodes without TSN capabilities connected to state-of-the-art TSN networks to communicate critical messages in a real-time fashion. We evaluate our approach using both synthetic and real-world test cases, comparing it with existing scheduling mechanisms. Furthermore, we use OMNET++ to validate the generated GCL schedules.

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1 Introduction

Standardized communication protocols allowing safety-critical communication with real-time guarantees are becoming increasingly relevant in application domains beyond aerospace, e.g., in industrial automation and automotive. Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) [16] amends the standard Ethernet protocol with real-time capabilities ranging from clock synchronization and frame preemption to redundancy management and schedule-based traffic shaping [4]. These novel mechanisms allow standard best-effort (BE) Ethernet traffic to coexist with isolated and guaranteed scheduled traffic (ST) within the same multi-hop switched Ethernet network.

44 The main enablers of this coexistence are a network-wide clock synchronization protocol
 45 (802.1ASrev [17]) defining a global network time, known and bounded device latencies (e.g.,
 46 switch forwarding delays), and a Time-Aware Shaper (TAS) mechanism [15] with a global
 47 communication schedule implemented in so-called Gate Control Lists (GCLs), facilitating
 48 ST traffic with bounded latency and jitter in isolation from BE communication. The TAS
 49 mechanism is implemented as a gate for each transmission queue that either allows or denies
 50 the sending of frames according to the configured GCL schedule.

51 The schedule generation for GCLs [4, 23, 20] has focused on enforcing deterministic
 52 transmission with isolation and compositional system design for ST flows requiring end-to-
 53 end guarantees. Craciunas et al. [4] proposed a Satisfiability Modulo Theories (SMT)-based
 54 method that binds a transmission slot (window) to at most one ST frame producing a schedule
 55 with 0-jitter and defined end-to-end latencies critical flows. Deterministic transmission and
 56 forwarding is enabled by isolating critical streams either in time or in different traffic classes.
 57 A drawback of this model is that the solution space may be significantly reduced, and the
 58 number of GCL entries may be too high for the storage capabilities of TSN devices [21].
 59 In [23], multiple ST frames are allowed to share a transmission slot (window), and hence
 60 they may delay each other (if they are not isolated in the space domain). Hence, [23] relaxes
 61 the 0-jitter assumption while still maintaining deterministic end-to-end temporal behavior.
 62 However, both approaches necessitate that the traffic leaves the sending end systems in a
 63 scheduled and synchronized fashion (i.e., requiring TSN capabilities on both end systems
 64 and switches) since the schedule controls the transmission and forwarding of frames from
 65 sending node to receiving node within the network, requiring that the interference between
 66 ST frames is either 0 or bounded by the schedule construction.

67 The limitation of previous approaches requiring end systems to be scheduled and
 68 synchronized to the network, i.e., to have 802.1Qbv and 802.1ASrev TSN capabilities,
 69 is often not realistic since many systems use, e.g., off-the-shelf microcontrollers, industrial
 70 PCs, and sensor nodes without TSN mechanisms. Hence, there is a need for GCL synthesis
 71 mechanisms that can schedule TSN networks with unscheduled and unsynchronized end
 72 systems in real-world applications. Other work, c.f. [21, 12], introduce class-based GCLs
 73 without the requirement for synchronized end systems. However, their scheduling models are
 74 quite limited, requiring all sending windows to be aligned among all switches and not using
 75 formal verification methods for the delay analysis within the scheduling step.

76 In this paper, we relax the requirement that end-systems need to be synchronized and/or
 77 scheduled and consider relative offsets of windows on different nodes. We intertwine the worst-
 78 case delay analysis from [31] with the scheduling step in order to generate correct schedules
 79 where the end-to-end requirements of ST flows are met. Furthermore, we describe different
 80 TSN scheduling approaches that have been proposed in the literature (see Table 3 for an
 81 overview) and compare them to our flexible window-based approach. We define the analysis-
 82 driven window optimization problem resulting from our more flexible approach with the goal
 83 to be able to enlarge the solution space, reduce computational complexity, and apply it to
 84 end-systems without TSN mechanisms. Depending on industrial applications' requirements,
 85 our evaluation can help system designers choose the most appropriate combination of
 86 configurations for their use-case. The main contributions of the paper are:

- 87 • We propose a novel flexible window-based scheduling method that does not individually
 88 schedule ST frames and flows but rather schedules open gate windows for individually
 89 scheduled queues. Hence, we can support non-deterministic queue states and hence
 90 networks with unscheduled and/or unsynchronized end-systems by integrating the WCD
 91 Network Calculus (NC) analysis into the scheduling step. The NC analysis is used to

construct a worst-case scenario for each flow to check its schedulability, considering arbitrary arrival times of flows and the open GCL window placements.

- We compare and evaluate our flexible window-based scheduling method with existing scheduling methods for TSN networks. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work comparing such mechanisms for TSN.
- We propose a proxy function as an extension for the analysis in [31] and implement it in our problem formulation.
- We formulate and solve a window optimization problem that uses the proxy function and provides timing guarantees for real-time flows even in systems with unscheduled and unsynchronized end systems.
- We evaluate the proposed approach on both synthetic and real-world test cases, validating the correctness and the scalability of our implementation and use the OMNET++ simulator to validate the generated solutions.

We start by presenting a review of related research, focusing on the existing scheduling mechanisms that we compare our work to, in Sect. 2. We introduce the system, network, and application models, as well as a description of the main TSN standards, in Sect. 3. We outline the problem formulation in Sect. 4. In Sect. 5, we present the novel scheduling mechanism and the optimization strategy based on the Constraint Programming (CP) followed by the comparison and evaluation results in Sect. 6. We conclude the paper in Sect. 7.

2 Related Work

Since its introduction, significant research efforts have focused on studying the real-time properties of Time-Sensitive Networking enabled by mechanisms such as 802.1Qbv and 802.1Asrev and the resulting TSN scheduling problems. In [7] the TSN scheduling problem is reduced to having one single queue for ST traffic and solving it using Tabu Search, as well as an optimization that reduces the number of guard-bands in order to optimize bandwidth usage. The work in [13] proposes a scheduling model for TSN networks in industrial automation with different traffic types and a hierarchical scheduling procedure for isochronous traffic.

The most relevant work for providing real-time communication properties in TSN networks (and to which we compare our approach to) has been presented in [4, 23, 20]. The main goal of these works is to allow temporal isolation and compositional system design for ST flows with end-to-end guarantees and deterministic communication behavior. The work in [4], which we call *OGCL*, presents a solution that generates the most deterministic and strict schedules for TSN. The scheduling constraints result in frame transmission with 0 jitter in each hop and guaranteed end-to-end latency. The deterministic behavior comes from the frame-based scheduling approach, which does not allow any variation in the transmission times and thus no interference between ST frames even when placed in the same queue. The work in [20] maintains the strict determinism but solves the problem using heuristics instead of SMT-solvers in order to improve scalability. Additionally, the ST schedules are generated such that the worst-case delays of AVB streams are minimized. The scheduling approach in [23], which we call *Frame-to-Window-based*, relaxes the 0-jitter constraint of [4] and thus allows more variance in the transmission times of frames along the hops of the TSN network. This increases the solution space at the expense of increased complexity in the correctness constraints. This method is also window-based, as is ours, but requires a unique mapping between GCL windows and frames in order to avoid non-deterministic delays in the queues.

The mentioned approaches require an essential property, namely, that both the end-systems and switches have TSN capabilities (i.e., are in a scheduled and synchronized fashion).

138 Thus, the schedule controls the transmission and forwarding of frames from a sending node
 139 to a receiving node within the network, requiring that the interference between ST frames is
 140 either 0 or bounded by the schedule construction. The open gate windows are then either a
 141 result of the frame transmission schedule [4, 20] or are uniquely associated with predefined
 142 subsets of frames [23]. However, the above property is a significant limitation. In many
 143 use cases, the endpoints (e.g., off-the-shelf) sensors, microcontrollers, industrial PCs, and
 144 edge devices do not have TSN capabilities (i.e., the 802.1Qbv timed-gate mechanism or
 145 the time-synchronization protocol of 802.1ASrev). The different scheduling mechanisms
 146 described above that we compare our work to are summarized in Table 3.

147 The work in [21] proposed a similar window-based approach (WND) but without the
 148 CP-based solution and with a very limited model since the offsets of the windows on different
 149 nodes are not considered, thereby essentially limiting the mechanisms by requiring all windows
 150 to be aligned among all switches. Moreover, [21] uses a less advanced analysis step (c.f. [30])
 151 in the scheduling decisions and a simpler heuristic approach. In [12], a class-based GCL was
 152 proposed without per-flow scheduling nor requirement of synchronized end-systems. The
 153 method proposed in [12] for calculating the worst-case delay bounds, unlike our approach, is
 154 not based on any formal verification methods (e.g., network calculus). The worst-case delay
 155 calculation is overly pessimistic for small-scale networks and not safe for large-scale networks.

156 Classical approaches like strict priority (SP) and AVB [14] do not require a time-gate
 157 mechanism and also work with unscheduled end-systems. In order to provide response-
 158 time guarantees, a worst-case end-to-end timing analysis through methods like network
 159 calculus [22, 5] or Compositional Performance Analysis (CPA) [6] are used. In [32, 33, 1],
 160 the rate-constrained (RC) flows of TTEthernet [18, 25] are analyzed using network calculus.
 161 Other works, such as [28, 19], study the response-time analysis for TDMA-based networks
 162 under the strict priority (SP) and weighted round-robin (WRR) queuing policies. Zhao et
 163 al. [31] present a worst-case delay analysis, which we use in this paper, for determining the
 164 interference delay between ST traffic on the level of flexible GCL windows.

165 In [26], the authors present hardware enhancements to standard IEEE 802.1Qbv bridges
 166 (along with correctness constraints for the schedule generation) that remove the need for
 167 the isolation constraints between frames scheduled in the same egress queue defined in [4].
 168 Another hardware adaptation for TSN bridges, which has been proposed by Heilmann et
 169 al. [11] is to increase the number of non-critical queues in order to improve the bandwidth
 170 utilization without impacting the guarantees for critical messages.

171 **3 System Model**

172 This section defines our system model for which we summarize the notation in Table. 1.

173 **3.1 Network Model**

174 We represent the network as a directed graph $G = (\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{E})$ where $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{ES} \cup \mathbf{SW}$ is the set of
 175 end systems (ES) and switches (SW) (also called nodes), and \mathbf{E} is the set of bi-directional full-
 176 duplex physical links. An ES can receive and send network traffic while SWs are forwarding
 177 nodes through which the traffic is routed. The edges \mathbf{E} of the graph represent the full-duplex
 178 physical links between two nodes, $\mathbf{E} \subseteq \mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{V}$. If there is a physical link between two nodes
 179 $v_a, v_b \in \mathbf{V}$, then there exist two ordered tuples $[v_a, v_b], [v_b, v_a] \in \mathbf{E}$. An equivalence between
 180 output ports $p \in P$ and links $[v_a, v_b] \in \mathbf{E}$ can be drawn as each output port is connected to
 181 exactly one link. A link $[v_a, v_b] \in \mathbf{E}$ is defined by the link speed C (Mbps), propagation delay
 182 d_p (which is a function of the physical medium and the link length), and the macrotick mt .

■ **Table 1** Summary of notations

Symbol	System model
$G = (\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{E})$	Network graph with the set of nodes (\mathbf{V}) and links (\mathbf{E})
$[v_a, v_b] \in \mathbf{E}$	Link
$[v_a, v_b].C, [v_a, v_b].mt$	Link speed and macrotick
$p \in P$	Output port
$p.Q$	Eight priority queues in an output port p
$q \in p.Q_{ST}$	A queue used for ST traffic in p
$\langle \phi, w, T \rangle_q$	GCL configuration for a queue $q \in p.Q_{ST}$, where $q.\phi$, $q.w$, and $q.T$ are the window offset, the window length, and the window period for a queue q , respectively.
$f.l, f.T, f.P, f.D$	Payload size, period, priority, and deadline of a flow $f \in \mathcal{F}$
$f.r = [[v_1, v_2], \dots, [v_{n-1}, v_n]]$	Route for a flow $f \in \mathcal{F}$

183 The macrotick is the length of a discrete time unit in the network, defining the granularity
 184 of the scheduling timeline [4]. Without loss of generality, we assume $d_p = 0$ in this paper.

185 As opposed to previous work, we do not require that end-system are either synchronized
 186 or scheduled. Since ESs can be unsynchronized and unscheduled, they transmit frames
 187 according to a strict priority (SP) mechanism. Switches still need to be synchronized and
 188 scheduled using the 802.1ASrev and 802.1Qbv, respectively.

189 3.2 Switch Model

190 Fig. 1a depicts the internals of a TSN switch. The switching fabric decides, based on the
 191 internal routing table to which output port p a received frame will be forwarded. Each egress
 192 port has a priority filter that determines in which of the available 8 queues (traffic-classes) of
 193 that port a frame will be put. Each priority queue $q \in p.Q$ stores the frames to be forwarded
 194 in first-in-first-out (FIFO) order. Similar to [4], a subset of the queues ($p.Q_{ST}$) is used for ST
 195 traffic, while the rest ($p.\bar{Q}$) are used for non-critical communication. As opposed to regular
 196 802.1Q bridges, where enqueued frames are sent out according to their respective priority, in
 197 802.1Qbv bridges, there is a Time-Aware Shaper (TAS), also called timed-gate, associated
 198 with each queue and positioned behind it. A timed-gate can be either in an *open* (O) or
 199 *closed* (C) state. When the gate is open, traffic from the respective queue is allowed to be
 200 transmitted, while a closed gate will not allow transmission, even if the queue is not empty.
 201 When multiple gates are open simultaneously, the highest priority queue has preference,
 202 blocking others until it is empty or the corresponding gate is closed. The 802.1Qbv standard
 203 includes a mechanism to ensure that no frames can be transmitted beyond the respective
 204 gate's closing point. This look-ahead checks whether the entire frame present in the queue
 205 can be fully transmitted before the gate closes and, if not, it will not start the transmission.

206 The state of the queues is encoded in a GCL. A fundamental difference to the similar
 207 technology TTEthernet (SAE AS6802) [18], is that in TSN the scheduling is done on the
 208 level of traffic-classes instead of on an individual frame level [3]. Hence, an imperfect time
 209 synchronization, frame loss, ingress policing (c.f. [4]), or the variance in the arrival of frames
 210 from unscheduled and/or unsynchronized ESs may lead to non-determinism in the state of
 211 the egress queues and, as a consequence, in the whole TSN network. If the state of the queue
 212 is not deterministic at runtime, the order and timing of the sending of ST frames can vary
 213 dynamically. In Fig. 1b, the schedule for the queue of the (simplified) switch SW, opens for
 214 two frames and then, sometime later, for the duration of another two frames. The arrival

■ **Figure 1** Switch internals and non-deterministic queue states due to variations in frame arrivals from unscheduled and/or unsynchronized ESs.

215 of frames from unscheduled and/or unsynchronized end systems may lead to a different
 216 pattern in the egress queue of the switch, as illustrated in the top and bottom figures of
 217 Fig. 1b. Note that we do not actually know the arrival times of the frames, and what we
 218 depict in the figure are just two scenarios to illustrate the non-determinism. There may be
 219 scenarios where one of the frames, e.g., frame “2”, arrives much later. This variance makes
 220 it impossible to isolate frames in windows and obtain deterministic queue states, and, as a
 221 consequence, deterministic egress transmission patterns, as required by previous methods for
 222 TSN scheduling (e.g. [4, 23, 20, 7]). We refer the reader to [4] for an in-depth explanation of
 223 the TSN non-determinism problem.

224 The queue configuration is expressed by a tuple $q = \langle Q_{ST}, \overline{Q} \rangle$. The decision in which
 225 queue to place frames is taken either according to the priority code point (PCP) of the VLAN
 226 tag or according to the priority assignment of the IEEE 802.1Qci mechanism. In order to
 227 formulate the scheduling problem, the GCL configuration is defined as a tuple $\langle \phi, w, T \rangle_q$ for
 228 each queue $q \in p.Q_{ST}$ in an output port p , with the window offset ϕ , window length w and
 229 window period T .

230 3.3 Application Model

231 The traffic class we focus on in this paper is scheduled traffic (ST), also called time-sensitive
 232 traffic. ST traffic is defined as having requirements on the bounded end-to-end latency
 233 and/or minimal jitter [4]. Communication requirements of ST traffic itself are modeled with
 234 the concept of flows (also called streams), representing a communication from one sender
 235 (talker) to one or multiple receivers (listeners). We define the set of ST flows in the network
 236 as \mathcal{F} . A flow $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is expressed as the tuple $\langle l, T, P, D \rangle_f$, including the frame size, the flow
 237 period in the source ES, the priority of the flow, and the required deadline representing
 238 the upper bound on the end-to-end delay of the flow. The route for each flow is statically
 239 defined as an ordered sequence of directed links, e.g., a flow $f \in \mathcal{F}$ sending from a source ES
 240 v_1 to another destination ES v_n has the route $r = [[v_1, v_2], \dots, [v_{n-1}, v_n]]$. Without loss of
 241 generality, the notation is simplified by limiting the number of destination ES to one, i.e.,
 242 unicast communication. Please note that the model can be easily extended to multicast
 243 communication by adding each sender-receiver pair as a stand-alone flow with additional
 244 constraints between them on the common path.

4 Problem Formulation

The problem formulation is as follows: Given (1) a set of flows \mathcal{F} with statically defined routes \mathcal{R} , and (2) a network graph G , we are interested in determining GCLs, which is equivalent to determining (i) the offset of windows $q.\phi$, (ii) the length of windows $q.w$, and (iii) the period of windows $q.T$ such that the deadlines of all flows are satisfied and the overall bandwidth utilization (defined in Sect. 5.1) is minimized.

Let us illustrate the importance of determining optimized windows. Recall that with flexible window-based scheduling we do not know the arrival times of frames, and frames of different ST flows may interfere with each other. Frames that arrive earlier will delay frames that arrive later; also, a frame may need to wait until a gate is open, or arrive at a time just before a gate closure and cannot fit in the interval that remains for transmission.

We illustrate in Fig. 2 three window configurations (a), (b), and (c), motivating the need to optimize the windows. The vertical axis represents each egress port in the network, and the horizontal axis represents the timeline. The tall grey rectangles give the gate open time for a priority queue. As mentioned, we do not know the arrival times of the frames, thus it is necessary to provide a formal analysis method to ensure real-time performance. In this paper, the timing guarantees are provided for a given window configuration using the Network Calculus (NC)-based approach from [31] to determine the worst-case end-to-end delay bounds (WCDs) for each flow. In the motivational example, the WCDs are determined by constructing a worst-case scenario for each flow. Hence, in Fig. 2 we show worst-case scenarios. The red and blue rectangles in the figure represent ST frames' transmission. There are two periodic flows f_1 (blue rectangles) and f_2 (red rectangles) with the same frame size and priority. We use the arrows pointing down to mark the arrival time for ST frames creating the worst-case case for f_2 . Let us assume that the deadline of each flow equals its period $f_i.T$. In each configuration in Fig. 2 we show that arrival scenario which would lead to the worst-case situation for frame f_2 , i.e., the largest WCD for f_2 .

Since the ESs are unscheduled (without TAS) and/or without time synchronization

Figure 2 Motivational example showing the importance of optimizing the windows. Note that the arrival times of frames are not known beforehand, hence we decided to illustrate in each configuration (a) to (c) an arrival scenario that leads to the worst-case delay for frame f_2 .

272 capabilities, the frames can arrive and be transmitted by the ES at any time (the offset of
 273 a periodic flow on the ES is in an arbitrary relationship with the offsets of the windows in
 274 the SWs). However, on the switches, frame transmissions are allowed to be forwarded only
 275 during the scheduled window. The worst-case for f_2 happens when the frame (1.1) of f_1
 276 arrives on $[ES_1, SW_1]$ slightly earlier than the frame (2.1) of f_2 arrives on $[ES_2, SW_1]$, and
 277 at the same time, they arrive on the subsequent egress port $[SW_1, SW_2]$ at a time when the
 278 remaining time during the current window is smaller than the frame transmission time. In
 279 this case, the guard band delays the frames until the next window slot.

280 With the windows configuration in Fig. 2(a), the WCD of f_2 is larger than its deadline,
 281 i.e., $WCD(f_2) > f_2.T$, hence, f_2 is not schedulable. If the window period is narrowed
 282 down, as shown in Fig. 2(b), the WCD of f_2 satisfies its deadline. However, there is a large
 283 bandwidth usage occupied by the windows. Fig. 2(c) uses the same window period as in
 284 Fig. 2(a) but changes the window offset. As can be seen in the figure, the WCD of the flow
 285 f_2 is also smaller than its deadline $f_2.T$, and compared with Fig. 2(b), the bandwidth usage
 286 of the windows is reduced. With the increasing complexity of the network, e.g., multiple
 287 flows joining and leaving at any switch in the network and/or an increased number of ST
 288 flows and priorities, an optimized window configuration cannot be done manually; therefore,
 289 optimization algorithms are needed to solve this problem.

290 5 Optimization Strategy

291 The problem presented in the previous section is intractable. The decision problem associated
 292 with the scheduling problem has been proved to be (NP)-complete in the strong sense [24].
 293 Hence, we use an optimization strategy, called Constraint Programming-based Window
 294 Optimization (CPWO), which is more suitable to find good solutions in a reasonable time.

295 CPWO takes as the inputs the architecture and application models and outputs a set of
 296 the best solutions found during search (see Fig. 3). We use Constraint Programming (CP)
 297 to search for solutions (the “CP solver” box). CP performs a systematic search to assign
 298 the values of variables to satisfy a set of constraints and optimize an objective function,
 299 see the “CP model” box: the sets of variables are defined in Sect. 5.2, the constraints in
 300 Sect. 5.3 and the objective function in Sect. 5.1. A feasible solution is a valid solution that is
 301 schedulable, i.e., the worst-case delays (WCDs) of streams are within their deadlines. Since
 302 it is impractical to check for schedulability within a CP formulation, we employ instead the
 303 Network Calculus (NC)-based approach from [31] to determine the WCDs, see the “WCD
 304 Analysis” box in Fig. 3. The WCD Analysis is called every time the CP solver finds a
 305 “new solution” which is valid with respect to the CP constraints. The “new solution” is not

■ **Figure 3** Overview of our proposed CPWO optimization strategy

306 schedulable if the calculated latency upper bounds are larger than the deadlines of some
 307 critical streams.

308 Although CP can perform an exhaustive search and find the optimal solution, this is
 309 infeasible for large networks. Instead, CPWO employs two strategies to speed up the search
 310 to find optimized schedulable solutions in a reasonable time, at the expense of optimality.

311 (i) A metaheuristic search traversal strategy: CP solvers can be configured with user-
 312 defined search strategies, which enforce a custom order for selecting variables for assignment
 313 and for selecting the values from the variable’s domain. Here, we use a *metaheuristic* strategy
 314 based on Tabu Search [2].

315 (ii) A timing constraint specified in the CP model that prunes the search space: Ideally,
 316 the WCD Analysis would be called for each new solution. However, an NC-based analysis is
 317 time-consuming, and it would slow down the search considerably if called each time the CP
 318 solver visits a new valid solution. Hence, we have introduced “search pruning” constraints
 319 in the CP model (the “Timing (pruning)” constraints in the “CP model” box in Fig. 3),
 320 explained in detail in Sect. 5.4.

321 These timing constraints implement a crude analysis that indicates if a solution may
 322 be schedulable and are solely used by the CP solver to eliminate solutions from the search
 323 space. These constraints may lead to both “relaxed-pruning” scenarios that are actually
 324 unschedulable or “aggressive-pruning” scenarios that eliminate solutions that are schedulable.
 325 The proxy function (pruning constraint) can thus be parameterized to trade-off runtime
 326 performance for search-space pruning in the CP-model.

327 The timing constraints assume that for a given stream, its frames in a queue will be
 328 delayed by other frames in the same queue, including a backlog of frames of the same
 329 stream. A parameter \mathcal{B} is used to adjust the number of frames in the backlog, tuning the
 330 pruning level of the CP model’s timing constraints. Note that NC still checks the actual
 331 schedulability, so it does not matter if the CP analysis is too relaxed—this will only prune
 332 fewer solutions, slowing down the search. However, using overly aggressive pruning runs the
 333 risk of eliminating schedulable solutions of good quality. We consider that \mathcal{B} is given by
 334 the user, controlling how fast to explore the search space. In the experiments, we adjusted
 335 \mathcal{B} based on the feedback from the WCD Analysis and the pruning constraint. If, during a
 336 CPWO run, the pruning constraint from Sect. 5.4 was invoked too often, we decreased \mathcal{B} , as
 337 it was pruning too aggressively; otherwise, if the WCD analysis was invoked too often and
 338 was reporting that the solutions were schedulable, we increased \mathcal{B} .

339 We first define the terms needed for the CP model in Table. 2. Then, we continue with
 340 the definition of the objective function, model variables, and constraints of the CP model.

■ **Table 2** Definition of terms used in CP model formulation

Term	Definition
$\mathcal{N}(P)$	Total number of windows assigned to priority queues
$\mathcal{K}(p)$	Hyperperiod of the port p
$\mathcal{L}(q)$	Maximum size of any frame from all flows assigned to the queue q
$\mathcal{GB}(q)$	Maximum transmission time of ST frames competing in the queue q
$\mathcal{R}(q)$	All flows assigned to the queue q
$\mathcal{X}(q)$	All flows arriving from a switch and assigned to the queue q

341 5.1 Objective Function

342 The CP solver uses the objective function Ω , which minimizes the average bandwidth usage:

$$343 \quad \forall p \in P, \forall q \in p.Q : \Omega = \frac{\sum \frac{q.w}{q.T}}{\mathcal{N}(P)}. \quad (1)$$

344

345 The average bandwidth usage is calculated as the sum of each window's utilization, i.e., the
 346 window length over its period, divided by the total number of windows in the CP model.
 347 Note that solutions found by a CP solver are guaranteed to satisfy the constraints defined in
 348 Sect. 5.3. In addition, the schedulability is checked with the NC-based WCD Analysis [31].

349 5.2 Variables

350 The model variables are the offset, length, and period of each window, see Sect. 3.2. For
 351 each variable, we define a domain which is a set of finite values that can be assigned to the
 352 variable. CP decides the values of the variables as an integer from their domain in each
 353 visited solution during the search. The domains of offset $q.\phi$, length $q.w$, and period $q.T$
 354 variables are defined, respectively, by

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall p \in P, \forall q \in p.Q : \\ & 0 < q.T \leq \frac{\mathcal{K}(p)}{[v_a, v_b].mt}, \quad 0 \leq q.\phi \leq \frac{\mathcal{K}(p)}{[v_a, v_b].mt}, \\ & \frac{\mathcal{L}(q)}{[v_a, v_b].mt \times [v_a, v_b].C} + \mathcal{GB}(q) \leq q.w \leq \frac{\mathcal{K}(p)}{[v_a, v_b].mt}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

355

356 The domain of the window period is defined in the range from 0 to the hyperperiod of the
 357 respective port p , i.e., the Least Common Multiple (LCM) of all the flow periods forwarded
 358 via the port. The window period is an integer and cannot be zero. The domain of the window
 359 offset is defined in the range from 0 to the hyperperiod of the respective port p . Finally, the
 360 domain of the window length is defined in the range from minimum accepted window length
 361 to the hyperperiod of the respective port p . The minimum accepted window length is the
 362 length required to transfer the largest frame from all flows assigned to the queue q , protected
 363 by the guard band $\mathcal{GB}(q)$ of the queue. A port p is attached to only one link $[v_a, v_b]$; and
 364 values and domains are scaled by the macrotick mt of the respective link.

365 5.3 Constraints

366 The first three constraints need to be satisfied by a valid solution: (1) the window is valid, (2)
 367 two windows in the same port do not overlap, and (3) windows' bandwidth is not exceeded.
 368 The last two constraints reduce the search space by restricting the periods of (4) queues and
 369 (5) windows to harmonic values in relation to the hyperperiod. Harmonicity may eliminate
 370 some feasible solutions but we use this heuristic strategy to speed up the search.

371 (1) The **Window Validity Constraint** (Eq. (3)) states that the offset plus the length of a
 372 window should be smaller or equal to the window's period:

$$373 \quad \forall p \in P, \forall q \in p.Q : \quad (q.w + q.\phi) \leq q.T. \quad (3)$$

374 (2) **Non-overlapping Constraint** (Eq. (4)). Since we search for solutions in which windows
 375 of the same port do not overlap, the opening or closing of each window on the same port

■ **Figure 4** Example capacity and transmission demand for a window.

376 (defined by its offset and the sum of its offset and length, respectively) is not in the range of
 377 another window, over all period instances:

$$\begin{aligned}
 378 \quad & \forall p \in P, \forall q \in p.Q, \forall q' \in p.Q, T_{q,q'} = \max(q.T, q'.T), \forall a \in [0, T_{q,q'}/q.T], \forall b \in [0, T_{q,q'}/q'.T] : \\
 379 \quad & (q.\phi + q.w + a \times q.T) \leq (q'.\phi + b \times q'.T) \vee (q'.\phi + q'.w + b \times q'.T) \leq (q.\phi + a \times q.T) \\
 380 \quad & \hspace{15em} (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

381 (3) The **Bandwidth Constraint** (Eq. (5)) ensures that all the windows have enough
 382 bandwidth for the assigned flows:

$$383 \quad \forall p \in P, \forall q \in p.Q, \forall f \in \mathcal{F}(q) : \frac{q.w}{q.T} \geq \sum \frac{f.l}{f.T}. \quad (5)$$

384 where $\mathcal{F}(q)$ is the set of flows assigned to the queue q .

385 (4) The **Port Period Constraint** (Eq. (6)) imposes that the periods of all the queues in a
 386 port should be harmonic. This constraint is used to avoid window overlapping as well as
 387 reducing the search space.

$$388 \quad \forall p \in P, \forall q \in p.Q, \forall q' \in p.Q : (q.T \% q'.T = 0) \vee (q'.T \% q.T = 0). \quad (6)$$

389 (5) The **Period Limit Constraint** (Eq. (7)) reduces the search space by considering window
 390 periods $q.T$ that are harmonic with the hyperperiod of the port $\mathcal{K}(p)$ (divide it):

$$391 \quad \forall p \in P, \forall q \in p.Q : \mathcal{K}(p) \% q.T = 0. \quad (7)$$

392 5.4 Timing constraints

393 As mentioned, it is infeasible to use a Network Calculus-based worst-case delay analysis to
 394 check the schedulability of *each* solution visited. Thus, we have defined a *Timing Constraint*
 395 as a way to prune the search space. Every solution that is not eliminated via this timing
 396 constraint is evaluated for schedulability with the NC WCD analysis. The timing constraint
 397 is a heuristic that prunes the search space of (potentially unschedulable) solutions; it is

398 not a sufficient nor a necessary schedulability test. The timing constraint is related to the
 399 optimality of the solution, not to its correctness in terms of schedulability. A too aggressive
 400 pruning may eliminate good quality solutions, and too little pruning will slow down the
 401 search because the NC WCD analysis is invoked too often.

402 The challenge is that the min+ algebra used by NC cannot be directly expressed in
 403 first-order formulation of CP. However, the NC formulation from [31] has inspired us in
 404 defining the CP timing constraints. The *Timing Constraint* is defined in Eq. (8) and uses
 405 the concepts of *window capacity* \mathcal{W}_C and *transmission demand* \mathcal{W}_D to direct the CP solver
 406 to visit only those solutions where the *capacity* of each window, i.e., the amount of time
 407 available to transmit frames assigned to its queue, is greater than or equal to its transmission
 408 *demand*, i.e., the amount of transmission time required by the frames in the queue. A window
 409 capacity larger than the transmission demand indicates that a solution has high chances to
 410 be schedulable:

$$411 \quad \forall p \in P, \forall q \in p.Q : \mathcal{W}_D \leq \mathcal{W}_C. \quad (8)$$

412 Thus, we first calculate the capacity \mathcal{W}_C of each window within the hyperperiod. This
 413 capacity is similar to the NC concept of a service curve, and its calculation is similar to the
 414 service curves proposed in the literature [27] for resources that use Time-Division Multiple
 415 Access (TDMA), which is how our windows behave. For e.g., a window with a period of
 416 $10 \mu s$, a length of $4 \mu s$, and an offset of $3 \mu s$; forwards 150 bytes over a 100 Mbps link in a
 417 hyperperiod of $30 \mu s$. In Fig. 4a, the capacity of such a window is depicted where the blue
 418 line shows the throughput of the window for transferring data. The capacity increases when
 419 the window opens (the rising slopes of the curve). The effect of window offset on the capacity
 420 (the area under the curve) can be observed in the figure. The function \mathcal{W}_C calculates the
 421 area under the curve to characterize the amount of capacity for a window in a hyperperiod,
 422 defined in Eq. (9), where the link $[v_a, v_b]$ is attached to the port p and assigned to the queue q ;
 423 and function \mathcal{Y} captures the transmission time of a single byte through link $[v_a, v_b]$.

424 To calculate the area under the curve, we consider 3 terms that are S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 . They
 425 represent the total area under the curve caused by the window length, the window closure in
 426 the remainder of the window period, and the window period, respectively. The \mathcal{W}_C value of
 427 the example in Fig. 4a is $2,250 \text{ Bytes} \times \mu s$, where the S terms are shown.

$$428 \quad \begin{aligned} & \forall p \in P, \forall q \in p.Q : \\ & I = \frac{\mathcal{K}(p)}{q.T}, \quad J = \frac{(q.w - \mathcal{GB}(q)) \times \mathcal{Y}([v_a, v_b])}{[v_a, v_b].C}, \\ & S_1 = I \times \frac{q.w \times J}{2}, \quad S_2 = I \times (q.T - q.w. - q.\phi) \times J, \\ & S_3 = \frac{I \times (I - 1)}{2} \times q.T \times J, \quad \mathcal{W}_C = S_1 + S_2 + S_3 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

429 Secondly, we calculate the transmission demand \mathcal{W}_D using Eq. (10), where the function $\mathcal{R}(q)$
 430 captures all the flows that are assigned to the queue q . The transmission demand is inspired
 431 by the *arrival curves* of NC. These are carefully determined in NC considering that the
 432 flows pass via switches and may change their arrival patterns [31]. In our case, we have
 433 made the following simplifying assumptions in order to be able to express the “transmission
 434 demand” in CP. We assume that all flows are strictly periodic and arrive at the beginning of
 435 their respective periods. This is “optimistic” with respect to NC in the sense that NC may
 436 determine that some of the flows have a bursty behavior when they reach our window. To
 437 compensate for this, we consider that those flows that arrive from a switch may be bursty

438 and thus have a backlog \mathcal{B} of frames that have accumulated; flows that arrive from ESs do
 439 not accumulate a backlog. Fig. 4b shows three flows, f_1 to f_3 , and only f_3 arrives from a
 440 switch and hence will have a backlog of frames captured by the flow denoted with f'_3 (we
 441 consider a \mathcal{B} of 1 in the example). We also assume that the backlog f'_3 will not arrive at
 442 the same time as the original flow f_3 , and instead, it is delayed by a period. Again, this
 443 is a heuristic used for pruning, and the actual schedulability check is done with the NC
 444 analysis. So, the definition of the “transmission demand” does not impact correctness, but,
 445 as discussed, it will impact our algorithm’s ability to search for solutions.

446 Since, in our case, the deadlines can be larger than the periods, we also need to consider
 447 for each flow bursts of frames coming from SWs and an additional frame for each flow coming
 448 from ESs (the ES periods are not synchronized with the SWs GCLs). Since we do not
 449 perform a worst-case analysis, we instead use a backlog parameter \mathcal{B} , which captures the
 450 possible number of delayed frames in a burst within a flow forwarded from another SW. Note
 451 that as explained in the overview at the beginning of Sect. 5, \mathcal{B} is a user-defined parameter
 452 that controls the “pruning level” of our timing constraint, i.e., how aggressively it eliminates
 453 candidates from the search space.

454 We give an example in Fig. 4b where the flows $f_1 < 50, 5, 0, 5 >$ and $f_2 < 60, 6, 0, 6 >$
 455 have been received from an ES and the flow $f_3 < 100, 15, 0, 15 >$ has been received from a
 456 SW. For the flow f_3 forwarded from a previous switch, we consider that one instance of the
 457 flow (determined by the backlog parameter $\mathcal{B} = 1$), let us call it f'_3 , may have been delayed
 458 and received together with the current instance f_3 . This would cause a delay in the reception
 459 of the flows in the current node. The reception curve in Fig. 4b is the sum of curves for each
 460 stream separately in a hyperperiod of $30 \mu s$.

461 We give the general definition of the transmission demand value \mathcal{W}_D as the area under
 462 the curve for the accumulated data amount of received flows and backlogs of the flows
 463 arrived from switches in a hyperperiod. For calculating the transmission demand \mathcal{W}_D , we
 464 consider 2 terms that are A_1 and A_2 . The term A_1 calculates the area under the curve for
 465 the accumulated data of all flows assigned to the queue q captured by $\mathcal{R}(q)$, in a hyperperiod.
 466 Any frames of all flows $\mathcal{R}(q)$ have arrived at the beginning of their period. The term A_2
 467 calculates the area under the curve for the accumulated backlog data of the flows arrived
 468 from a switch captured by $\mathcal{X}(q)$. The backlog data of the flows $\mathcal{X}(q)$ are delayed for a period
 469 and controlled by \mathcal{B} , which captures the number of backlogs. The function \mathcal{W}_D returns
 470 $16,650 \text{ Bytes} \times \mu s$ in our example, see also Fig. 4b for the values of the terms A_1 and A_2 .

$$\forall p \in P, \forall q \in p.Q, \forall f \in \mathcal{R}(q), \forall f' \in \mathcal{X}(q) :$$

$$I = \frac{\mathcal{K}(p)}{f.T}, \quad I' = \frac{\mathcal{K}(p)}{f'.T}$$

$$A_1 = \frac{I \times (I + 1)}{2} \times f.T \times f.l,$$

$$A_2 = \frac{I' \times (I' + 1 - 2 \times \mathcal{B})}{2} \times f'.T \times f'.l,$$

$$471 \quad \mathcal{W}_D = A_1 + A_2 \tag{10}$$

472 Please note that the correctness of the constraints (Eq. (3), (4), (5)) follows from the
 473 implicit hardware constraints of 802.1Q(bv) (see the discussion in [4, 23]) while other
 474 constraints (Eq. (6), (7)) are used to limit the placement of GCL windows and are not related
 475 to correctness, just to optimality. Since the transmission of frames is decoupled from the
 476 GCL windows, the schedule’s correctness concerning the end-to-end latency of streams is
 477 always guaranteed due to the NC analysis, which is intertwined in the schedule step.

478 **6 Evaluation**

479 In this section, we first discuss the ST scheduling approaches in the literature, motivating
 480 our proposed approach called Flexible Window-based GCL (*FWND*), see Sect. 6.1. We
 481 give details of our setup and test cases in Sect. 6.2 and evaluate our windows optimization
 482 solution CPWO for *FWND* on synthetic and real-world test cases on Sect. 6.3 and Sect. 6.4,
 483 respectively. We also compare the CPWO results with the related work and validate the
 484 generated GCLs with OMNET++ in Sect. 6.5.

485 **6.1 Scheduling Approaches**

486 The related work on ST scheduling using 802.1Qbv consists of: (i) zero-jitter GCL (0GCL) [4,
 487 20], (ii) Frame-to-Window-based GCL (FGCL) [23], and (iii) Window-based GCL (WND) [21].

488 We summarize the requirements of the ST scheduling approaches from the related work
 489 and our *FWND* approach in the first column of Table 3. The first three requirements refer to
 490 the device capabilities needed for the different approaches, and the next seven rows present
 491 the constraints and isolation requirements. The last two rows present the requirements of
 492 the complexity of the optimization problem that needs to be solved to provide a solution for
 493 the respective approach.

494 To better understand the fundamental differences and the similarities (in terms of the
 495 imposed correctness constraints and schedulability parameters) between our work and the
 496 approaches that require synchronized and scheduled end systems, we briefly reiterate the
 497 formal constraints of previous work. We describe, based on [4, 3, 23], the relevant scheduling
 498 constraints for creating correct TSN schedules when using frame- and window-based methods.
 499 Table 3 shows which of these are needed by which approach.

500 We adapt some notations from [4, 3] to describe the constraints and assume certain
 501 simplifications without loss of generality, e.g. the macrotick is the same in all devices, all

■ **Table 3** Time-Sensitive Message Transmission Approaches in TSN

Requirements	0GCL [4][20]	FGCL [23]	WND [21]	FWND
Device Capabilities	802.1Qbv	802.1Qbv	802.1Qbv	802.1Qbv
ES Capabilities	scheduled	scheduled	non-scheduled	non-scheduled
SW Capabilities	scheduled	scheduled	scheduled	scheduled
Frame Constraint	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Link Constraint ¹⁾	Yes	Yes	No	No
Bandwidth Constraint	No	No	No	Yes
Flow Transmission Constraint ²⁾	Yes	Yes	No	No
Frame-to-Window Assignment	No	Yes	No	No
Window Size Constraint	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Flow/Frame Isolation	Yes	Yes	No	No
End-to-end Constraint	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Schedule synthesis	Yes (intractable)	Yes (intractable)	No (only windows)	No (only windows)
Timing analysis required	No	No	Yes	Yes

1) No two frames routed through the same physical link can overlap in the time domain, also named “Ordered Windows Constraint” in [23].

2) The propagation of frames of a flow follows the sequential order along the path of the flow, also named “Stream Constraint” in [23].

flows have only one frame per period, the propagation delay d_p is 0. We refer the reader to [4, 23] for a complete and generalized formal definition of the correctness constraints. We denote the messages (frames) of a flow f_i on a link $[v_a, v_b]$ as $m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}$. A message $m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}$ is defined by the tuple $\langle m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}. \phi, m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}. l \rangle$, denoting the transmission time and duration of the frame on the respective link [4, 3].

Frame Constraint. Any frame belonging to a critical flow has to be transmitted between time 0 and its period T_i . To enforce this, we have the frame constraint from [4]:

$$\forall f_i \in \mathcal{F}, \forall [v_a, v_b] \in f_i.r : \left(m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}. \phi \geq 0 \right) \wedge \left(m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}. \phi \leq f_i.T - m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}. l \right).$$

Link Constraint. Since there can only be one frame at a time on a physical link, we enforce that no two frames sent on the same egress port may overlap in the time domain. The link constraint adapted from [4] is hence:

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall [v_a, v_b] \in \mathbf{E}, \forall m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}, m_j^{[v_a, v_b]} (i \neq j), \forall a \in [0, hp_i^j / f_i.T - 1], \forall b \in [0, hp_i^j / f_j.T - 1] : \\ & \left(m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}. \phi + a \times f_i.T \geq m_j^{[v_a, v_b]}. \phi + b \times f_j.T + m_j^{[v_a, v_b]}. l \right) \vee \\ & \left(m_j^{[v_a, v_b]}. \phi + b \times f_j.T \geq m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}. \phi + a \times f_i.T + m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}. l \right), \end{aligned}$$

where $hp_i^j = lcm(f_i.T, f_j.T)$ is the hyperperiod of f_i and f_j .

Flow Transmission Constraint. The (optional) flow transmission constraint enforces that a frame is forwarded by a device only after it has been received at that device also taking into account the network precision, denoted with δ :

$$\forall f_i \in \mathcal{F}, \forall [v_a, v_x], [v_x, v_b] \in f_i.r, \forall m_i^{[v_a, v_x]}, \forall m_i^{[v_x, v_b]} : m_i^{[v_x, v_b]}. \phi - \delta \geq m_i^{[v_a, v_x]}. \phi + m_i^{[v_a, v_x]}. l.$$

End-to-End Constraint. The maximum end-to-end latency constraint (expressed by the deadline $f_i.D$) enforces a maximum time between the sending and the reception of a flow. We denote the sending link of stream f_i with $src(f_i)$ and the last link before the receiving node with $dest(f_i)$. The maximum end-to-end latency constraint [4] is hence

$$\forall f_i \in \mathcal{F} : m_i^{dest(f_i)}. \phi + m_i^{dest(f_i)}. L - m_i^{src(f_i)}. \phi \leq f_i.D - \delta.$$

Here again the network precision δ needs to be taken into account since the local times of the sending and receiving devices can deviate by at most δ .

802.1Qbv Flow/Frame Isolation. Due to the non-determinism problem in TSN (c.f. Sect. 3.2), previous solutions (e.g., [4, 23]) need an isolation constraint that maintains queue determinism. We refer the reader to [4] for an in-depth explanation and only summarize here the flow and frame isolation constraint adapted from [4]. Let $m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}$ and $m_j^{[v_a, v_b]}$ be, respectively, the frame instances of $f_i \in \mathcal{F}$ and $f_j \in \mathcal{F}$ scheduled on the outgoing link $[v_a, v_b]$ of device v_a . Flow f_i arrives at the device v_a from some device v_x on link $[v_x, v_a]$. Similarly, flow f_j arrives from another device v_y on incoming link $[v_y, v_a]$. The simplified flow isolation constraint adapted from [4], under the assumption that the macrotick of the involved devices is the same, is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \forall [v_a, v_b] \in \mathbf{E}, \forall m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}, m_j^{[v_a, v_b]} (i \neq j), \forall a \in [0, hp_i^j / f_i.T - 1], \forall b \in [0, hp_i^j / f_j.T - 1] : \\ & \left(m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}. \phi + a \times f_i.T + \delta \leq m_j^{[v_y, v_a]}. \phi + b \times f_j.T \right) \vee \\ & \left(m_j^{[v_a, v_b]}. \phi + b \times f_j.T + \delta \leq m_i^{[v_x, v_a]}. \phi + a \times f_i.T \right). \end{aligned}$$

540 Here again $hp_i^j = lcm(f_i.T, f_j.T)$ is the hyperperiod of f_i and f_j . The constraint ensures
 541 that once a flow arrives at a device, no other flow can enter the device until the first flow has
 542 been sent.

543 The above constraints apply to frames that are placed in the same queue on the egress
 544 port. However, the scheduler may choose (if possible) to place streams in different queues,
 545 isolating them in the space domain. Hence, the complete constraint [4] for frame/flow
 546 isolation for two flows f_i and f_j scheduled on the same link $[v_a, v_b]$ can be expressed as

$$547 \quad \left(\Phi_{[v_a, v_b]}(f_i, f_j) \right) \vee \left(m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}.q \neq m_j^{[v_a, v_b]}.q \right),$$

548
 549 with $m_i^{[v_a, v_b]}.q \leq N_{tt}$ and $m_j^{[v_a, v_b]}.q \leq N_{tt}$ and where $\Phi_{[v_a, v_b]}(f_i, f_j)$ denotes either the flow
 550 or frame isolation constraint from before.

551 **Decoupling of frames.** So far, the constraints were applicable on the level of frames,
 552 and the open windows of the GCLs were constructed from the resulting frame schedule. The
 553 approach in [23] decouples the frame transmission from the respective open gate windows
 554 defined in the GCLs, similar to our approach¹. However, in [23] the requirement is that
 555 there is a unique assignment of which frames are transmitted in which windows, although
 556 also multiple frames can be assigned to be sent in the same window. Hence, the assignment
 557 of frames and, consequently, the length of each gate open window are, therefore, an output
 558 of the scheduler. Therefore, we have to construct additional constraints when (partially)
 559 decoupling frames from windows. For a more in-depth description and formalization of these
 560 constraints we refer the reader to [23].

561 *Frame-to-Window Assignment.* The frame-to-window assignment restricts a frame to be
 562 assigned to a specific window, although multiple frames can be assigned to the same window.

563 *Window Size Constraint.* The length of the gate open window has to be restricted to the
 564 sum of the frame lengths that have been assigned to it.

565 Comparing the existing approaches with the one proposed in this paper, we see that the
 566 choice of scheduling mechanism is, on the one hand, highly use-case specific and, on the other
 567 hand, is constrained by the available TSN hardware capabilities in the network nodes. While
 568 the frame- and window-based methods from related work result in precise schedules that
 569 emulate either a 0- or constrained-jitter approach (e.g., like in TTEthernet), they require
 570 end systems to not only be synchronized to the network time but also the end devices to
 571 have 802.1Qbv capabilities, i.e., to be scheduled. This limitation might be too restrictive for
 572 many real-world systems relying on off-the-shelf sensors, processing, and actuating nodes.
 573 While our *FWND* method overcomes this limitation, it does require a worst-case end-to-end
 574 analysis that introduces a level of pessimism into the timing bounds, thereby reducing the
 575 schedulability space for some use cases. However, as seen in Table 3, our method does not
 576 require many of the constraints imposed on the flows and scheduled devices from previous
 577 work, thereby reducing the complexity of the schedule synthesis.

578 6.2 Test Cases and Setup

579 *FWND* is implemented in Java using Google OR-Tools [10] and the Java kernel of the RTC
 580 toolbox [29] and was run on a computer with an i9 CPU at 3.6 GHz and 32 GB of RAM.
 581 We have considered a time limit of 10 to 90 minutes, depending on the test case size. The
 582 *macrotick* and \mathcal{B} parameters are set to 1 μ s and 1, respectively, in all the test cases.

¹ Note that [4, 23, 20] cannot be used in our context because they require scheduled and synchronized ESs

■ **Table 4** Details of the synthetic test cases

No.	Network Topology	Total No. of SWs	Total No. of ESs	Total No. of Flows	Hyperperiod (μs)
1	SRM	2	3	9	15,000
2	SRM	3	3	11	70,000
3	SRM	3	4	15	70,000
4	MR	4	6	15	30,000
5	MR	4	8	21	210,000
6	MR	5	11	27	210,000
7	MM	4	5	13	15,000
8	MM	6	12	30	210,000
9	MM	7	13	35	210,000
10	ST	3	4	7	15,000
11	ST	3	6	12	15,000
12	ST	3	7	16	105,000
13	MT	7	8	18	105,000
14	MT	7	8	25	105,000
15	MT	7	12	32	210,000

583 We have generated 15 synthetic test cases that have different network topologies (three
584 test cases for each topology in Fig. 5) inspired by industrial and automotive application
585 requirements. Similar to [34], the network topologies are small ring & mesh (SRM), medium
586 ring (MR), medium mesh (MM), small tree-depth 1 (ST), and medium tree-depth 2 (MT).
587 Flows of the test cases are randomly generated, and the message sizes are randomly chosen
588 between the minimum and the maximum Ethernet frame size, while their periods are selected
589 from the set $P = \{1,500, 2,500, 3,500, 5,000, 7,500, 10,000\}$, all in μs . The physical link
590 speed is set for 100 Mbps. The details of the synthetic test cases are in Table 4 where the
591 second column shows the topology of the test cases, and the number of switches, end systems,
592 and flows are shown in columns 3 to 6.

593 We have also used two realistic test cases: an automotive case from General Motors (GM)
594 and an aerospace case, the Orion Crew Exploration Vehicle (CEV). The GM case consists of
595 27 flows varying in size between 100 and 1,500 bytes, with periods between 1 ms and 40 ms
596 and deadlines smaller or equal to the respective periods. The CEV case is larger, consisting
597 of 137 flows, with sizes ranging from 87 to 1,527 bytes, periods between 4 ms and 375 ms ,
598 and deadlines smaller or equal to the respective periods. The physical link speed is set for
599 1000 Mbps. More information can be found in the corresponding columns in Table 5. Use
600 cases use the same topologies as in [9] and [31], and we consider that all flows are ST.

601 6.3 Evaluation on synthetic test cases

602 We have evaluated our CPWO solution for $FWND$ on synthetic test cases. The results are
603 depicted in Table 6 where we show the objective function value (average bandwidth Ω from
604 Eq. (1)) and the mean WCDs. For quantitative comparison, we have also reported the results
605 for the three other ST scheduling approaches: $OGCL$, $FGCL$, WND . $OGCL$ and $FGCL$ were
606 implemented by us with a CP formulation using the constraints from [4] and [23], respectively,
607 where these techniques were proposed. The WND method has been implemented with the
608 heuristic presented in [21], but instead of using the WCD analysis from [30], we extend it
609 to use the analysis from [31] instead, in order not to unfairly disadvantage WND over our
610 CPWO solution. Note that the respective mean worst-case end-to-end delays in the table are
611 obtained over all the flows in a test case, from a single run of the algorithms, since the output

■ **Figure 5** Network topologies used in the test cases

612 of the algorithms is deterministic based on worst-case analyses, not based on simulations.

613 It is important to note that *OGCL* and *FGCL* are presented here as a means to evaluate
 614 CPWO; however, they are *not producing valid solutions* for our problem, which considers
 615 unscheduled end systems, see Table 3 for the requirements of each method. As expected, when
 616 end systems are scheduled and synchronized with the rest of the network as is considered in
 617 *OGCL* and *FGCL*, we obtain the best results in terms of bandwidth usage (Ω) and WCDs,
 618 with the comment that *OGCL* may further reduce the WCDs compared to *FGCL*.

619 The only other approach that has similar assumptions to our *FWND* is *WND* from [21].
 620 As we can see from Table 6, in comparison to *WND*, our CPWO solution can slightly reduce
 621 the bandwidth usage. The most important result is that CPWO significantly reduces the
 622 WCDs compared to *WND*, with an average of 104% and up to 437% for some test cases
 623 such as TC13. This means that we are able to obtain schedulable solutions in more cases
 624 compared to the work in [21].

625 Also, when comparing the WCDs obtained by our *FWND* approach with the case when
 626 the end systems are scheduled, i.e., *OGCL* and *FGCL*, we can see that the increase in WCDs
 627 is not dramatic. This means that for many classes of applications, which can tolerate a slight
 628 increase in latency, we can use our CPWO approach to provide solutions for more types of
 629 network implementations, including those that have unscheduled and/or unsynchronized end
 630 systems. In addition, due to the complexity of their CP model, it takes a long runtime to
 631 obtain solutions for *OGCL* and *FGCL*, and the CP-model for *FGCL* run out of memory for
 632 some of the test cases (the NA in the table). As shown in the last two columns of Table 6,
 633 where we present the runtimes of *OGCL* and *FWND*, *FWND* reduces the runtime significantly.
 634 The reason for reduced runtime with *FWND* is that the CP model has to determine values
 635 for fewer variables compared to *OGCL*. *FWND* introduces 3 variables (offset, period and
 636 length) for each window (queue) in the network, whereas *OGCL* introduces a variable for each
 637 frame of each flow. The number of variables in the *OGCL* model depends on the hyperperiod,
 638 the number of flows, and the flow periods, whereas the number of variables in the *FWND*
 639 model depends on the number of switches and used queues.

■ **Table 5** Performance of CPWO for *FWND* on realistic test cases

	ORION (CEV)	GM
ES	31	20
SW	15	20
Flows	137	27
Mean WCDs (μs)	10,376	1,981
Ω ($\times 1000$)	435	84
Runtime (s)	891	17

■ **Table 6** Evaluation results on synthetic test cases

No.	Ω^1 for OGCL	Ω^1 for FGCL	Ω^1 for WND	Ω^1 for FWND	Mean worst-case e2e-delay for OGCL (μs)	Mean worst-case e2e-delay for FGCL (μs)	Mean worst-case e2e-delay for WND (μs)	Mean worst-case e2e-delay for FWND (μs)	Mean Runtime for OGCL (ms)	Mean Runtime for FWND (ms)
1	35	35	614	510	192	126	1838	1556	215	8
2	25	22	640	528	246	151	2461	1806	895	12
3	15	15	549	495	175	486	1964	1384	1518	22
4	13	13	330	285	160	776	2925	1832	525	16
5	14	NA ²⁾	295	285	131	NA ²⁾	2838	2347	5187	16
6	13	NA ²⁾	275	205	129	NA ²⁾	2953	1976	6291	17
7	12	12	238	204	125	764	2913	1561	1152	35
8	13	NA ²⁾	238	202	114	NA ²⁾	2878	1725	7603	36
9	12	NA ²⁾	217	191	122	NA ²⁾	3074	1927	9171	56
10	8	8	329	265	136	2284	4397	4327	2611	165
11	10	10	381	302	159	984	3047	2057	2840	231
12	11	NA ²⁾	516	321	187	NA ²⁾	2543	1326	4650	260
13	10	10	401	302	101	561	2529	471	978	130
14	9	9	611	402	120	785	2254	628	1256	162
15	9	NA ²⁾	544	413	114	NA ²⁾	2680	713	6116	163

1) Values are multiplied by 1000

2) Ran out of memory

(a) Mean WCDs vs. simulated delays for FWND

(b) Mean WCDs comparison for TC12

■ **Figure 6** Worst-case delay comparison with simulated response times.

6.4 Evaluation on realistic test cases

640

641 We have used two realistic test cases to investigate the scalability of CPWO and its ability
 642 to produce schedulable solutions for real-life applications. The results of the evaluation are
 643 presented in Table 5 where the mean WCDs, objective value Ω , and runtime for the two test
 644 cases are given. As we can see, CPWO has successfully scheduled all the flows in both test
 645 cases. Note that once all flows are schedulable, CPWO aims at minimizing the bandwidth.
 646 This means that CPWO may be able to achieve even smaller WCD values at the expense
 647 of bandwidth usage. In terms of runtime, the CEV test case takes longer since it has 864
 648 variables, whereas GM has only 102 variables in the CP models.

6.5 Validating the solutions with OMNET++

649

650 We have used the OMNET++ simulator with the TSN NeSTiNg extension [8] to validate
 651 the generated GCLs. Thus, we have synthesized the GCLs for all approaches on all synthetic
 652 test cases, and we have observed that the GCLs are correct and the simulation behaves
 653 as expected. The mean WCDs of CPWO for the synthetic test cases and the worst-case
 654 latency observed during multiple OMNET++ simulations (with the windows from CPWO)
 655 are depicted in Fig. 6a. As expected, the latency values reported by OMNET++ are smaller
 656 than the WCDs, as reported by the WCD Analysis from [31]. This is because a simulation
 657 cannot easily uncover the worst-case behavior. However, the simulation indicates the average
 658 behavior, and small delays mean that even for unscheduled/unsynchronized end systems,
 659 we are able to obtain solutions that are not only schedulable (WCDs are smaller than

■ **Table 7** Scalability evaluation of CPWO

No.	Total No. of Flows	Total No. of ESs	Total No. of SWs	Mean WCDs μs	Largest deadline μs	Ω ($\times 1000$)
TC1	100	50	35	3,226	4,000	249
TC2	150	55	40	3,521	4,000	366
TC3	200	60	40	4,387	5,000	396
TC4	300	65	40	4,911	6,000	468
TC5	400	70	45	5,210	6,000	498
TC6	500	75	45	4,399	5,000	511

660 the deadlines) but also have good average behavior, where most of the time the delays
 661 are reasonable, even smaller than the static schedules obtained by *OGCL* and *FWND* for
 662 scheduled and synchronized ESs. The pessimism result of the WCD analysis is unavoidable
 663 in systems with un-synchronized and/or unscheduled end-systems; in practice, however,
 664 simulated delays are much smaller, as can be seen in Fig. 6a and Fig. 6b. We also show in
 665 Fig. 6b the simulated delays and WCDs for all flows of TC12. All the flows are schedulable,
 666 and, as expected, the simulated delays are smaller than the WCDs, calculated with the
 667 worst-case delay analysis derived in the work from [31].

6.6 Scalability Evaluation

669 We have investigated the scalability of CPWO on 6 larger test cases (TC1 to TC6), that
 670 have up to 120 devices (75 ESs and 45 SWs) and 500 flows. The results and the details of
 671 the test cases are presented in Table 7, where columns 2, 3, and 4 show the number of flows,
 672 end-systems, and switches, respectively. Columns 5, 6, and 7 show the mean WCD of flows in
 673 μs , the largest deadline of all flows in μs , and the objective value Ω , related to bandwidth, see
 674 Eq. (1). CPWO was able to generate schedulable solutions in all cases. Furthermore, CPWO
 675 is optimize the schedules for minimum bandwidth usage and has generated solutions that,
 676 besides being schedulable, have mean WCDs on average 14% smaller than the respective
 677 deadlines in all test cases.

7 Conclusions

679 We have presented a novel, more flexible heuristic schedule synthesis approach for TSN
 680 networks, which decouples the frame scheduling from the generation of time-aware shaper
 681 (TAS) windows. Our method eliminates the often-unrealistic constraint that end systems are
 682 scheduled and synchronized (i.e., they have TSN capabilities) required by previous methods
 683 to provide real-time guarantees for critical traffic in IEEE 802.1Qbv TSN networks. Our
 684 approach intertwines an existing worst-case delay analysis method with a CP-solver into a
 685 novel and scalable heuristic approach that uses a Tabu Search metaheuristic search strategy in
 686 the CP-solver. Furthermore, to improve scalability, we have proposed a novel *proxy function*
 687 which can be parametrized to trade-off runtime performance for search-space pruning in the
 688 CP-model. We evaluated our approach using synthetic and real-world test cases, comparing
 689 it with existing mechanisms and validated the generated schedules using OMNET++.

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